

TOGETHER IN ARCHIVAL DREAMS

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Abstract – The detailed processes in workflows for digital preservation can sometimes make the difference between a well-used, and successful system and one that fails to reach that goal. A collection of integrations and new software for the ArchivesSpace environment has given the Queensland State Archives a unique and seamless way for government agencies to transfer digital files, and a fully digital workflow through to long term preservation.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In 2020, Queensland State Archives (QSA) launched their new Archival Management System ArchivesSpace, which also delivered new systems for public and agency use - ArchivesSearch and ArchivesGateway respectively. In 2023, digital preservation capabilities were added to this software suite, and all four systems are tightly integrated providing a best-in-class user experience for all systems - both internal and external.

This poster highlights the most useful integrations in this ecosystem as selected by staff, developers, and external users. It specifically looks at the transfer workflow through to ingest, and digital preservation functions.

II. GOAL

The goal of this poster is to show some of the unique capabilities of QSA's system, to demonstrate how an interconnected set of systems designed with archives at front of mind, can deliver a seamless experience for all system users. Notable benefits include error resolution and support, live transfer status updates, centralised documentation and enhanced transparency and accountability.

The collaboration between QSA and Gaia Resources demonstrates how a partnership between an archival institution and an IT supplier can deliver an innovative and comprehensive suite of applications and workflows.

III. INTENDED AUDIENCE

Staff from all types of archival and other collecting organisations will be interested in the seamless workflows that provide an automated system, from agencies transferring digital files and metadata, through to ingest into the digital preservation system and the archival management system. Files are then automatically surfaced to the public system (when the material is open), and to the agency portal so that each agency can access the records they are responsible for, depending on their permissions.

Viewers will grasp how a coupled workflow, led by archivists and in collaboration with an IT supplier, enhances daily operations. A single point of truth and dataset ensures access to essential information without compromising efficiency.

IV. CONCLUSION

This automated end to end workflow within a set of tightly integrated systems allows a streamlined experience from digital material submission through to access and is believed to be unique in the world of digital preservation and archival management systems currently. The system and supported workflows will foster sustainable long-term digital preservation for QSA.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Stefania Di Maria, Principal Digital Preservation Advisor at QSA, has worked on the Digital Archiving program from its inception, including the design, build, and launch of The Digital Archive. With a Philosophy degree and a Graduate Certificate in Records Management and Archives, she is passionate about preserving digital records and ensuring their long-term accessibility through innovative archiving solutions.

Marcus Burke, Principal Technical Advisor, joined QSA in 2015 after working in various ICT roles over the last 17 years in both the private and public sector. Marcus worked on the project team that delivered ArchivesSpace, ArchivesGateway, ArchivesSearch and the digital preservation system, Archivematica. Marcus has a degree in Accounting & Finance.

Sarah Aldrich began working with Gaia Resources after a decade working in museums and archives in the US. She enjoys supporting the technical side of the systems she once relied upon. Sarah has a Masters degree in Byzantine Art History as well as diplomas in Museology and Information Technology.

Meg Travers worked in digital roles in government archives, libraries, and museums in Western Australia before joining Gaia Resources where she enjoys thorny digital preservation issues, and seeing all the amazing collections that exist around Australasia. She almost completed a PhD on preserving the musical instrument, the Trautonium.

